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DEVELOPING ENGLISH SKILLS IN BEGINNERS: EFFECTIVE METHODS AND CLASSROOM TECHNIQUES

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ABSTRACT

This thesis explores effective methods and techniques for teaching English to beginners. Beginning language learners require engaging and interactive approaches to language instruction that promote comprehension, retention, and confidence in using English. Key strategies include Total Physical Response (TPR), CLIL method (Content and Language Integrated Learning or subject-language integrated learning), visual aids, storytelling, role-playing, games and activities, dialogues and conversations, grammar instruction within context, peer interaction, and a multisensory approach. By tailoring lessons to students' interests and abilities, providing ample practice opportunities, and fostering a supportive learning environment, educators can effectively facilitate language acquisition at the initial stage.

Key words: language instruction, initial stage, Total Physical Response(TPR), CLIL, visual aids, conversational practice, peer interaction, language acquisition

May 6, 2021 a videoconference on measures to improve the system of teaching foreign languages was held under the chairmanship of the President Shavkat Mirziyoyev. At the conference «It is time to create a new system of teaching foreign languages in our country, which will become a solid foundation for the future. Since we set ourselves the goal of building a competitive state, from now on the graduates of schools, lyceums, colleges and universities must be fluent in at least two foreign languages. This strict requirement should become the main criterion for the work of the director of each educational institution», Shavkat Mirziyoyev said.[1]

After that, the Uzbekistan education system in teaching English has undergone a huge number of changes. Every teacher understands perfectly well that it is necessary to constantly look for such pedagogical technologies that could interest students and motivate them to study the subject.

The technology of active teaching methods (AMO technology) effectively solves the tasks set for education, and English language lessons in primary school are no exception.[2]

Let's look at some of them, the most common and most often used in foreign language lessons:

- group and pair work creates favorable conditions for the inclusion of all students in active work in the lesson. When organizing work in pairs and groups, each student thinks and has the opportunity to express his opinion. In groups, children learn from each other in the process of educational discussion and educational dialogue. It is especially important that the group form of work makes it possible to implement an individual approach in conditions of mass education, to organize the interaction of children to identify their individual abilities and needs;

- problem situations, in order to get out of which the student needs to make a decision and find an answer, and, in turn, for this he is forced to form new knowledge himself with the help of the teacher and other students, based on other people's professional experience, logic and common sense.

- business games are aimed at developing certain recipes for effective educational and professional activities. Games are an integral part of the life of schoolchildren; they have the opportunity to relieve unpleasant or forbidden experiences and embarrassment for the student's personality. The game should easily attract the child's unstable attention to the material, give new knowledge, and force him to think.

- the round table allows you to consolidate previously acquired knowledge, fill in missing information, develop problem-solving skills, and teach a culture of discussion. Along with the active exchange of knowledge, students develop professional skills to express thoughts, argue their ideas, justify proposed solutions and defend their beliefs. It is very important that the table is truly round, that the teacher is also a member of the

general circle, that the conversation takes place “eye to eye,” this will help students behave more openly and relaxed. It is interesting to have an object in the group (toy, key, rod, etc.) that the student must hold at the moment when he answers.

- the project method is a comprehensive teaching method that allows you to individualize the educational process, allowing the student to exercise independence in planning, organizing and monitoring their activities. Already in elementary school, children are involved in the development, implementation and presentation of a project.

The CLIL method (Content and Language Integrated Learning or subject-language integrated learning) has recently become increasingly popular in teaching English. Simply put, CLIL is the study in English (or another foreign language) of all or several subjects of the school curriculum - this could be the world around us, drawing, history, geography, social studies, mathematics, chemistry, biology, literature and even physical education.[3]

The TPR method is memorizing new words or phrases using gestures or following teacher commands. For example, for the word ball - ball, children pretend to make a gesture as if playing with a ball, for the word pen - pen - they pretend to write with an imaginary pen, etc. Indeed, children remember English words and phrases much better when they study supported by gestures. After all, visual-figurative thinking predominates among schoolchildren.[4]

Thus, the use of active learning methods in the classroom ensures a high level of student interest, their cognitive and creative activity, guarantees the creation of a situation of success for each student, which helps turn learning into a rich, high-quality, effective and psychologically comfortable process not only for students, but also for teachers.

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